

New records of Coleoptera (Insecta) from Kamchatka Krai and other regions of the Russian Far East

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Abstract

Twelve species of beetles (Coleoptera) from the families Dytiscidae, Hydrophilidae, Leiodidae, Nitidulidae, and Scaptiidae are recorded for the Kamchatka Krai for the first time. Two species, *Ilybius subaeneus* Erichson, 1837 (Dytiscidae) and *Cercyon emarginatus* Baranowski, 1985 **stat. rev.** (Hydrophilidae) are recorded for the Russian Far East for the first time, first from Kamchatka and second from Primorsky Krai. *Cercyon borealis* Baranowski, 1985 (Hydrophilidae) is recorded for the first time from Kamchatka and Jewish Autonomous Oblast. New data on the occurrence of the little-known *Leiodes shigehisai* Hoshina, 2012 (Leiodidae), on the Kamchatka Peninsula is provided. These new records increase the total number of beetle species known from the Kamchatka Krai to 865.

Keywords

Biodiversity, distribution, *Cercyon*, Dytiscidae, Hydrophilidae, Leiodidae, Nitidulidae, protected areas, Scaptiidae

Introduction

The third volume of the “Annotated Catalogue of the insects of the Russian Far East”, dedicated to beetles (Coleoptera), was published in 2025. The catalog includes data on 6.291 beetle species belonging to 1.826 genera and 114 families. In total, 852 species are known from Kamchatka (Sundukov 2025), with more than 100 species recorded from the Kronotsky State Nature Reserve (Ruchin and Esin 2025). This article provides a new records of beetles from five families previously non recorded from Kamchatka Krai.

Materials and methods

Field researches were conducted in 2025 across three municipal districts of Kamchatka Krai: Karaginsky (V.A. Netsvetaev), Ust-Bolsheretsky and Elizovsky (A.B. Ruchin, M.N. Esin), mostly on the territory of South Kamchatka federal sanctuary named after T.I. Shpilenok (South Kamchatka refuge) (Figure 1).

Material was collected using standard techniques (Golub et al. 2021). Aquatic beetles were collected using water hand net, terrestrial with soil pitfall, Merike (pan), Malaise, and fermental beer traps (Figure 2).

The nomenclature and species distribution in Russian Far East provided according to Annotated Catalogue of the Insects of the Russian Far East (Kirejtshuk 2025; Prokin and Petrov 2025; Prokin and Ryndevich 2025; Sergeev 2025; Zinchenko 2025), and for firstly recorded in Russian Far East *Ilybius subaeneus* Erichson, 1837 according to Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera (Hájek 2017).

To verify the identifications, specimens listed herein were compared with material from the following collections:

IBIW – Papanin Institute for Biology of Inland Waters Russian Academy of Sciences, Borok, Russia;

ZISP – Zoological Institute Russian Academy of Sciences, St. Petersburg, Russia;

ZMMU – Zoological Museum, M.V. Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow, Russia.

Results

An annotated list of beetle species new to the Kamchatka Peninsula is provided, based on the original data. Little-known species previously recorded in Kamchatka Krai are marked with an asterisk (*).

Figure 1. Map of the Far East and adjacent territories of Russia. 1–11 – the Russian Far East: 1 – Chukotka Autonomous Okrug, 2 – Magadan Oblast; 3 – Kamchatka Krai; 4, 5 – Khabarovsk Krai: 4 – north of the Tugur River (northern part), 5 – south of the Tugur River (southern part); 6 – Jewish Autonomous Oblast; 7 – Amur Oblast; 8, 9 – Primorsky Krai: 8 – north of the line between Lake Malaya Khanka–Rudnaya Pristan (northern part), 9 – south of the aforementioned line (southern part); 10 – Sakhalin Island; 11 – Kuril Islands: Northern – Shumshu, Paramushir and adjacent small islands, Central – from Onekotan to Urup, Southern – south of Urup. Red circles – main sampling locations: A – Karaginsky District, B – South Kamchatka refuge.

Figure 2. The main landscapes of the study area and some types of traps used for sampling: **A** – lake in the floodplain of Pylyunavayam River; **B** – lake in the floodplain of Gachyngvalovayam River; **C** – floodplain meadow, South Kamchatka refuge (cordon Travyanoy); **D** – mixed-grass meadow, South Kamchatka refuge (cordon Travyanoy); **E** – a glade, South Kamchatka refuge (cordon Ozernyi); **F** – pitfall trap; **G** – fermental beer trap; **H** – Merike traps.

Family DYTISCIDAE Leach, 1815***Ilybius subaeneus* Erichson, 1837**

Material. Karaginsky Distr., 11 km S of the mouth of Ken'guyayam River, 60°32'19.9"N 163°08'45.5"E, lakelet, 26.07.2025 V.A. Netsvetaev, 2 exs.

Remarks. The first record from the Russian Far East. This Holarctic species is not listed in the Annotated catalogue (Prokin and Petrov 2025), but known from eastern Siberia (Hájek 2017).

***Hydroporus sibiricus* J.R. Sahlberg, 1880**

Material. Karaginsky Distr., 11 km S of the mouth of Ken'guyayam River, 60°32'19.9"N 163°08'45.5"E, lakelet, 26.07.2025 V.A. Netsvetaev, 1 ex.

Remarks. The first record from Kamchatka. This species was known in the Russian Far East from Magadan Oblast (Prokin and Petrov 2025).

***Hygrotus (Leptolambus) novemlineatus* (Stephens, 1829)**

Material. Karaginsky Distr., 14 km N of the mouth of Gachyngvalovayam River, 60°09'51.1"N 163°22'32.4"E, lake, 24.07.2025 V.A. Netsvetaev, 2 exs.; Karaginsky Distr., 14 km E of the mouth of Pylyunavayam River, 60°28'16.5"N 163°28'46.7"E, lake, 01.08.2025 V.A. Netsvetaev, 3 exs.

Remarks. The first record from Kamchatka. This species was known in the Russian Far East from Magadan Oblast (Prokin and Petrov 2025).

Family HYDROPHILIDAE Latreille, 1802***Cercyon (Cercyon) borealis* Baranowski, 1985**

Figs 3A–C, 4A–F, 5A–G

Paratype. [Sweden] Dlr., [Dalarna] Näs, Gräsbgt. [Gräsberget], 10.7.1981, B. Ehnström, 1♀ (ZMMU).

Material. Ust-Bolsheretsky Distr., South Kamchatka refuge, near cordon Ozernyi, 51°29'01.7"N 157°02'01.7"E, pitfall traps, 29.07–10.08.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 1♀.

Additional material. Jewish Autonomous Oblast, Dechun, Amur River, near Radde vill., 130°45'E, 15.08.1978 Kurbatov leg., 1♀, *Cercyon borealis* det. Shatrovskiy, 1988 (ZMMU); Primorsky Krai, Sikhote-Alin Nature Reserve, floodplain of the Zabolochennaya River (44°31'57.0"N 136°12'06.5"E), 11.07.2018, M.E. Sergeev, 1♂, *Cercyon terminatus* det. Prokin, 2021 (IBIW); floodplain of the Rezvushka River (45°32'27.6"N 136°09'57.6"E), 28.05.2020, M.E. Sergeev, 1♂1♀, *Cercyon terminatus* det. Prokin, 2021 (IBIW); stream in valley of the Kolumbe River (45°19'56.6"N

136°08'11.4"E), 18.06.2015, M.E. Sergeev, 2♂♂1♀, *Cercyon terminatus* det. Prokin, 2021 (IBIW).

Remarks. The first record from Kamchatka and Jewish Autonomous Oblast. This species was known in the Russian Far East from Amur Oblast and southern part of Primorsky Krai (Prokin and Ryndevich 2025).

Family LEIODIDAE Fleming, 1821

Leiodes fracta (Seidliz, 1874)

Material. Ust-Bolsheretsky Distr., South Kamchatka refuge, cordon Ozernyi, 51°29'00.2"N 157°01'50.2"E, pitfall traps, 11–29.08.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 2 exs.; 51°28'51.6"N 157°02'11.0"E, pitfall traps, 11–29.08.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 2 exs.

Remarks. The first record from Kamchatka. This species was known in the Russian Far East from south of Primorsky Krai (Zinchenko 2025).

Leiodes obesa (W.L.E. Schmidt, 1841)

Material. Ust-Bolsheretsky Distr., South Kamchatka refuge, cordon Ozernyi, 51°28'52.3"N 157°02'13.6"E, glade, yellow pan traps, 26–28.07.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 1 ex.; 51°28'56.3"N 157°02'17.2"E, glade, yellow pan traps, 28–31.07.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 1 ex.; 51°28'51.6"N 157°02'11.0"E, pitfall traps 29.08–30.09.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 1 ex.; 51°28'51.6"N 157°02'11.0"E, pitfall traps, 11–29.08.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 1 ex.; 51°29'00.2"N 157°01'50.2"E, pitfall traps, 29.07–11.08.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 3 exs.; Ust-Bolsheretsky Distr., South Kamchatka refuge, cordon Travyanoy, 51°25'09.8"N 157°02'51.0"E, pitfall traps, 30.07–11.08.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 2 exs.

Remarks. The first record from Kamchatka. This species was known in the Russian Far East from Primorsky Krai and Kunashir Island (Zinchenko 2025).

Leiodes silesiaca (Kraatz, 1852)

Material. Ust-Bolsheretsky Distr., South Kamchatka refuge, cordon Ozernyi, 51°29'00.2"N 157°01'50.2"E, pitfall traps, 11–29.08.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 1 ex.

The first record from Kamchatka. This species was known in the Russian Far East from Primorsky Krai (Zinchenko 2025).

**Leiodes shigehisai* Hoshina, 2012

Material. Ust-Bolsheretsky Distr., South Kamchatka refuge, near cordon Ozernyi, 51°29'01.7"N 157°02'01.7"E, pitfall traps, 29.08–30.09.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 3 exs.

Remarks. The second record from Russia and Kamchatka. This species was described from Hokkaido, Japan (Hoshina 2012), and recorded from Kamchatka,

Kronotsky Nature Reserve (Sazhnev 2025), but overlooked in the Annotated catalogue (Zinchenko 2025).

***Leiodes rhaetica* (Erichson, 1845)**

Material. Ust-Bolsheretsky Distr., South Kamchatka refuge, cordon Travyanoy, 51°25'09.8"N 157°02'51.0"E, pitfall traps, 11–29.08.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 2 exs.; 51°25'09.8"N 157°02'51.7"E, Malaise trap, 29.08–06.09.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 1 ex.

Remarks. The first record from mainland Russia and Kamchatka. This species was known in the Russian Far East from Atlasov Island (Northern Kurils) (Zinchenko 2025).

Family NITIDULIDAE Latreille, 1802

***Eपुरaea (Eपुरaea) biguttata* (Thunberg 1784)**

Material. Elizovsky Distr., 4 km SW of Nikolaevka vill., 53°01'05.5"N 158°16'27.8"E beer trap, 02–13.08.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 2 exs.; Elizovsky Distr., 1 km S of Elizovo, 53°08'13.9"N 158°20'48.5"E, beer trap, 02–13.08.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 3 exs.

Remarks. The first record from Kamchatka. This species was known in the Russian Far East from Amur Oblast, Khabarovsk and Primorsky Krai, and Kunashir Island (Kirejtshuk 2025).

***Cychramus luteus* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Material. Ust-Bolsheretsky Distr., South Kamchatka refuge, cordon Travyanoy, 51°25'09.8"N 157°02'51.7"E, Malaise trap, 29.08–06.08.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 1 ex.

Remarks. The first record from Kamchatka. This species was known in the Russian Far East from Amur Oblast, Khabarovsk and Primorsky Krai, Sakhalin and Kunashir Islands (Kirejtshuk 2025).

***Cychramus variegatus* (Herbst, 1792)**

Material. Ust-Bolsheretsky Distr., South Kamchatka refuge, 3 km NW of cordon Ozernyi, 51°29'42.7"N 157°00'02.9"E, beer trap, 07–11.08.2025, M.N. Esin, 1 ex.; 51°28'53.8"N 157°02'12.1"E, beer trap, 26–30.07.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 1 ex.

Remarks. The first record from Kamchatka. This species was known in the Russian Far East from Amur Oblast, Khabarovsk and Primorsky Krai and Kunashir Island (Kirejtshuk 2025).

Family SCRAPTIIDAE Gistel, 1848

Anaspis (Anaspis) arctica Zettersted, 1828

Material. Ust-Bolsheretsk Distr., 23 km NE of Apacha, 53°01'53.4"N 157°19'20.2"E, beer trap on birch, 25–31.07.2025 A.B. Ruchin, 2 exs.

Remarks. The first record from Kamchatka. This species was known in the Russian Far East from Primorsky Krai and Sakhalin Island (Sergeev 2025).

Taxonomy notes

Before studying the type and additional material previously we mixed two species *Cercyon borealis* Baranowski, 1985 (see above) and *C. emarginatus* Baranowski, 1985, both collected in Primorsky Krai, under the name *C. terminatus* (Marsham, 1802). As a result, we erroneously established synonymy *C. emarginatus* Baranowski, 1985 with *C. terminatus* (Marsham, 1802) (Sazhnev et al. 2021).

The comparison of the specimen of *C. emarginatus* Baranowski, 1985 from Primorsky Krai with specimens of this species from Sweden, and specimens of *C. terminatus* (Marsham, 1802) (Figs 3F, 4K–M, 5P–W) confirmed the species rank of *C. emarginatus* Baranowski, 1985 according differential characters, listed in the original description (Baranowski 1985).

Cercyon (Cercyon) emarginatus Baranowski, 1985 stat. rev.

Figs 3D–E, 4G–J, 5H–O

Material. Primorsky Krai, Sikhote-Alin Nature Reserve, stream in valley of the Kolumbe River (45°19'56.6"N 136°08'11.4"E), 18.06.2015, M.E. Sergeev, 1♂ (IBIW). The first record from the Russian Far East!

Additional material studied. [Sweden] Dlr., [Dalarna] Nås, Gräsbgt. [Gräsbget], 18.8.1983, B. Ehnström, 2♀♀, [*Cercyon*] *emarginatus* det. R. Baranowski, 1983; [Sweden] Dlr., [Dalarna] Nås, Fleu, 05.11.1983, B. Ehnström, 1♂, [*Cercyon*] *emarginatus* det. R. Baranowski, 1983 (ZMMU).

Discussion

The species *Ilybius subaeneus* Erichson, 1837 and *Hydroporus sibiricus* J.R. Sahlberg, 1880, both new for Kamchatka, were collected together with *Agabus arcticus ochoticus* Poppius, 1908 in small lakelet near Ken'guyayam River. The third new dytiscid *Hygrotus novemlineatus* (Stephens, 1829) was a single species collected in lake near Gachyngvalovayam River, and in lake near Pylyunavayam River it was collected together with *Hydroporus nigellus* Mannerheim, 1853.

Figure 3. *Cercyon* spp., dorsal habitus: A–C – *Cercyon borealis* Baranowski, 1985 (A – Russia: Kamchatka Krai, South Kamchatka refuge; B – paratype, Sweden, ZMMU; C – Russia: Primorsky Krai, Sikhote-Alin Nature Reserve, Kolumbe River, IBIW); D–E – *Cercyon emarginatus* Baranowski, 1985 (D – Russia: Primorsky Krai, Sikhote-Alin Nature Reserve, IBIW; E – Sweden, ZMMU); F – *Cercyon terminatus* (Marsham, 1802) (Georgia: Borjomi, ZISP).

Figure 4. *Cerycion* spp., detail of morphology. **A–F** – *Cerycion borealis* Baranowski, 1985 (**A–B** – paratype, Sweden, ZMMU; **C–D** – Russia: Primorsky Krai, Sikhote-Alin Nature Reserve, Kolumbe River, IBIW; **E–F** – Russia: Kamchatka Krai, South Kamchatka refuge); **G–J** – *Cerycion emarginatus* Baranowski, 1985 (**G–H** – Russia: Primorsky Krai, Sikhote-Alin Nature Reserve, IBIW; **I–J** – Sweden, ZMMU); **K–M** – *Cerycion terminatus* (Marsham, 1802) (**K** – Uzbekistan: Tashkent, ZISP; **L–M** – Georgia: Borjomi, ZISP). **A, C, E, G, I, K, L** – clypeus, **B, D, F, H, J, M** – ventral view of pterothorax.

In addition to regionally new and listed above, the following species of dytiscids were collected in the Karaginsky District 23.07–03.08.2025: *Hydroporus fuscipennis* Schaum in Schaum & Kiesenwetter, 1867, *H. morio* Aubé, 1838, *H. umbrosus* (Gyllenhal, 1808), *Agabus discolor* (Harris, 1828), *A. clypealis* (Thomson, 1867), *A. coxalis ermaki* (Zaitzev, 1953), *Ilybius angustior* (Gyllenhal, 1808), *Colymbetes dolabratus* (Paykull, 1798), *Rhantus suturellus* (Harris, 1828), and *Dytiscus* sp. (larva). Thus, the detected local dytiscid fauna of the Karaginsky District represented mostly by the species with circumpolar Holarctic ranges, in two cases with eastern Palaearctic subspecies (*A. arcticus ochoticus*, *A. coxalis ermaki*), and some arcto-boreal Palaearctic (*H. novemlineatus*), amphi-Pacific (*H. sibiricus*), and temperate Transpalaearctic (*H. umbrosus*) elements.

Figure 5. The description is on the next page.

Figure 5. *Cercyon* spp., male genitalia: **A–G** – *Cercyon borealis* Baranowski, 1985 (Russia: Primorsky Krai, Sikhote-Alin Nature Reserve, Rezvushka River (**A**), Kolumbe River (**B–D, F, G**), Zabolochennaya River (**E**), IBIW); **H–O** – *Cercyon emarginatus* Baranowski, 1985 (**H–L** – Russia: Primorsky Krai, Sikhote-Alin Nature Reserve, IBIW; **M–O** – Sweden, ZMMU); **P–W** – *Cercyon terminatus* (Marsham, 1802) (**P–T** – Uzbekistan: Tashkent, ZISP; **U–W** – Russia: Lipetsk Oblast, Galichya Gora Nature Reserve, IBIW); **A** – aedeagus; **B, I, Q** – median lobe (penis); **C, H, M, P, U** – tegmen of aedeagus; **D, E, J, S** – 9th sternite; **F, R** – apex of median lobe; **G, L, O, T, W** – detail of apex of parameres; **K** – apex of 9th sternite.

Several species of terrestrial beetles were also collected in the South Kamchatka refuge: *Amara brunnea* (Gyllenhal, 1810) (Carabidae); *Catops lydiae* Iablokoff-Khznorian, 1970, *C. alsiosus mongolicus* Jeannel, 1936 (Leiodidae); *Nicrophorus investigator* Zetterstedt, 1824, *N. vespilloides* Herbst, 1783, *Phosphuga atrata* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Lordithon thoracicus thoracicus* (Fabricius, 1777), *Tachinus elongatus* Gyllenhal, 1810, *T. instabilis* Mäklin, 1853 (Staphylinidae); *Byrrhus pilula* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Byrrhidae); *Hypnoidus bicolor* (Eschscholtz, 1829), *Liotrichus affinis* (Paykull, 1800) (Elateridae); *Rhagonycha cembraicola* (Eschscholtz, 1822) (Cantharidae); *Meloe violaceus* Marsham, 1802 (Meloidae); *Epuraea boreella* (Zetterstedt, 1828), *E. contractula* J. Sahberg, 1889, *E. silacea* (Herbst, 1783) (Nitidulidae); *Oedemera virescens virescens* (Linnaeus, 1767) (Oedemeridae); *Corticarina minuta* (Fabricius, 1792) (Latridiidae); *Coccinella septempunctata* Linnaeus, 1758 (Coccinellidae) and *Galeruca tanacetii inciscollis* (Motschulsky, 1860) (Chrysomelidae).

Terrestrial beetles represented mostly by the species/subspecies with temperate Holarctic (*N. investigator*, *N. vespilloides*, *L. thoracicus thoracicus*, *T. elongatus*, *L. rhaetica*, *E. boreella*, *C. minuta*, *C. septempunctata*), temperate Transpalaeartic (*Ph. atrata*, *B. pilula*, *M. violaceus*, *E. biguttata*, *E. silacea*, *C. luteus*, *C. variegatus*, *O. virescens*), and boreal Transpalaeartic (*A. brunnea*, *C. borealis*, *L. fracta*, *L. obesa*, *L. silesiaca*, *E. contractual*, *A. arctica*) ranges; in two cases with boreal eastern Palaeartic (*C. alsiosus mongolicus*, *Rh. cembraicola*) and arcto-boreal amphipacific (*T. instabilis*, *H. bicolor*), and boreal western Pacific (*L. shigehisai*), boreal pan-Pacific (*C. lydiae*), arcto-boreal eastern Palaeartic (*G. tanacetii inciscollis*) and arcto-boreal Transpalaeartic (*L. affinis*) ranges.

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